

The True Cost of Militarization: A Decolonial Perspective on War, Occupation, and Sustainability from the Palestine Space Institute

Response to UNODA Call for Papers on the Impact of Military Expenditure on the SDGs

Institution: Palestine Space Institute (PSI)
Author: Sahba El-Shawa
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Contact: palestinespaceinstitute@gmail.com

PALESTINE SPACE INSTITUTE

Abstract

The global increase in military expenditure diverts crucial resources away from sustainable development initiatives, disproportionately affecting regions already subjected to militarization, colonial occupation, and systemic underdevelopment. Nowhere is this more evident than in the latest war on Gaza, where military aggression has led to mass displacement, destruction of infrastructure, and environmental devastation, directly undermining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). This paper examines how military spending exacerbates inequalities, particularly in the context of Palestine, and highlights the PSI Space and Military-Industrial Complex database, which documents the links between space technologies and militarization. Furthermore, this paper situates the war on Gaza within the broader context of eco-apartheid in Palestine, demonstrating how the Israeli military's excessive funding enables environmental destruction, resource theft, and systematic displacement in both Gaza and the West Bank. Drawing from PSI's research, this paper argues for an urgent shift towards demilitarization and resource reallocation to foster peace, resilience, and equity. Finally, it puts forward five policy recommendations in response to the United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs' call on the impact of the global increase in military expenditure on the achievement of the sustainable development goals.

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1. Introduction

Military expenditure has reached unprecedented levels globally, with nations prioritizing defense budgets over investments in sustainable development. The UN General Assembly's Pact for the Future recognizes the potential negative impacts of this trend, emphasizing the urgent need to reassess global spending priorities. For Palestine, where military occupation and aggression have entrenched economic, environmental, and social vulnerabilities, the implications of excessive military spending are particularly severe. This paper explores the impact of global and regional militarization on the SDGs, using Palestine as a case study.

The Palestine Space Institute (PSI) is a think tank dedicated to examining the intersections of space policy, sustainability, and decolonization, with a particular focus on the militarization of space and its entanglement with colonial and imperialist structures. PSI works to expose the role of space technologies in sustaining military occupations and war economies, particularly in Palestine.

Through initiatives such as the PSI Space and Military-Industrial Complex database, PSI tracks the involvement of space companies in the arms trade, particularly those that provide dual-use technologies for military operations, surveillance, and targeted warfare. PSI has documented how global aerospace and defense firms develop satellite reconnaissance and missile technologies that have been directly integrated into Israeli military campaigns against Gaza. These technologies, often co-developed by Israeli and Western defense contractors, illustrate how military investments in space are leveraged for both intelligence gathering and active warfare, further entrenching militarized violence and occupation.

Space activities have long been framed as endeavors of peaceful exploration and technological progress. However, many spacefaring nations and corporations engage in what PSI defines as "spacewashing," a process by which military and defense industries use space programs to deflect from their involvement in war and occupation. The impact of this militarization extends beyond immediate destruction, influencing economic disparities, technological accessibility, and environmental sustainability, all of which are directly linked to the SDGs.

The following sections outline the ways in which excessive military spending obstructs sustainable development. Drawing from PSI's research and advocacy work, we propose urgent policy recommendations to counteract the growing influence of military expenditure and advocate for the redirection of resources toward sustainability, peace, and technological self-determination.

2. Militarization and Its Impact on Sustainable Development

2.1. Economic Implications (SDG 1, SDG 8, SDG 9, SDG 10)

The allocation of vast financial resources to military activities comes at the expense of investments in poverty alleviation (**SDG 1 – No Poverty**), economic growth (**SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth**), infrastructure development (**SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure**), and reducing inequalities (**SDG 10 – Reduced Inequalities**). In Gaza and the West Bank, a system of apartheid has further entrenched economic disparity by restricting Palestinian access to land and water, limiting agricultural and industrial development.

The Israeli military's control over Palestinian land, resources, and trade routes prevents economic development from taking root. Agriculture is obstructed by the destruction of farmlands and water restrictions, while Palestinian industries are stifled by movement restrictions, supply chain disruptions, and targeted demolitions. The blockade on Gaza has further entrenched economic hardship, with entire sectors rendered non-functional due to limited access to materials, energy, and markets.

At the same time, global military industries continue to extract profit from this entrenched violence. Arms manufacturers, security firms, and defense contractors benefit from the continuous demand for surveillance, border enforcement, and advanced weaponry. This cycle ensures that economic disparity remains not only a consequence of military occupation but also a key driver of the war economy that sustains it.

2.2. Humanitarian Crisis and Basic Needs (SDG 2, SDG 3, SDG 4, SDG 6, SDG 7, SDG 11)

The war on Gaza has led to catastrophic shortages of food (**SDG 2 – Zero Hunger**), medicine and healthcare (**SDG 3 – Good Health and Well-Being**), and educational access (**SDG 4 – Quality Education**). Attacks on water infrastructure have severely impacted access to clean water and sanitation (**SDG 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation**), while deliberate destruction of electricity grids has cut off energy access (**SDG 7 – Affordable and Clean Energy**). The mass displacement of civilians further undermines the goal of sustainable and resilient cities (**SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities**).

Beyond Gaza, Palestinians in the West Bank face systematic restrictions that prevent access to basic resources. Water sources are controlled, schools are frequently demolished under the pretense of permit violations, and energy shortages remain persistent due to restrictions on infrastructure development. The continuous targeting of civilian areas

ensures that sustainable urban development remains impossible, with communities subjected to repeated cycles of destruction and displacement.

This weaponization of essential services ensures that Palestinians remain in a permanent state of crisis, where even the most fundamental aspects of sustainable living are systematically denied. The prioritization of military objectives over humanitarian needs perpetuates a structure in which life is rendered precarious by design.

2.3. Environmental Destruction and Climate Injustice (SDG 13, SDG 15)

Military activities contribute significantly to environmental degradation through land destruction, resource depletion, and pollution, exacerbating climate vulnerabilities (**SDG 13 – Climate Action**) and damaging ecosystems (**SDG 15 – Life on Land**). The PSI Space and Military-Industrial Complex database has documented how military operations impact environmental sustainability, linking the destruction of natural resources to broader patterns of military-industrial activity.

In Gaza, airstrikes and bombardments have resulted in toxic pollution, soil degradation, and chemical contamination that make land unusable for future agricultural production. In the West Bank, land confiscation for settlement expansion has led to the destruction of Palestinian agricultural heritage, with indigenous trees uprooted and farmland replaced by industrial zones that serve settler populations. The deliberate contamination of land through military waste, industrial runoff, and denial of sanitation infrastructure ensures that environmental degradation remains a tool of systematic oppression.

Additionally, eco-apartheid in both Gaza and the West Bank manifests through water theft, agricultural destruction, and systematic environmental degradation. Israeli military policies have deliberately blocked Palestinian access to vital resources, exacerbating climate vulnerabilities while enabling settlement expansion. This weaponization of the environment, coupled with excessive military funding, has entrenched a system where sustainability is unattainable for Palestinians under occupation.

Palestine exemplifies how military expenditure not only hinders economic and social development but also systematically obstructs environmental and technological progress. The war on Gaza has further reinforced the barriers to sustainable development, with targeted destruction of universities, research centers, and technological infrastructure preventing Palestinian institutions from fully engaging in global sustainability efforts.

However, the impact of military spending on environmental sustainability is not limited to Palestine. Global military industries are among the largest contributors to climate destruction, yet they remain largely excluded from international climate agreements and sustainability initiatives. The continued prioritization of military expansion over ecological

restoration ensures that environmental collapse is accelerated, while those living under occupation suffer the most immediate consequences.

2.4. Space Militarization and the Threat to Global Security (SDG 16)

The expansion of military expenditures into outer space through satellite-based surveillance, missile defense systems, and space-based warfare further destabilizes global security and peace (**SDG 16 – Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions**). PSI's research highlights how space militarization perpetuates neocolonial power structures and obstructs the potential of space as a shared domain for scientific collaboration and sustainable development.

The Israeli military's reliance on "battle-tested" dual-use space technologies underscores how excessive military funding enables repression on Earth while advancing space militarization. Palestine serves as an example of how military priorities in space do not serve sustainable development but instead reinforce existing systems of militarized control.

The increasing militarization of space poses a broader threat to global security. The deployment of missile defense systems, intelligence satellites, and other military assets in space strengthens existing power imbalances, ensuring that space remains an extension of terrestrial conflicts rather than a neutral domain for peaceful cooperation. The unchecked expansion of space-based military technologies undermines disarmament efforts and ensures that conflict remains embedded within the very infrastructure of future technological development.

Furthermore, PSI has introduced the term spacewashing to describe how states and corporations use space exploration, space applications, and space imaginaries to deflect from the militarism of the space-industrial complex. Just as states engage in greenwashing, pinkwashing, and bluewashing to obscure environmental and human rights violations, the space sector has increasingly been used to manufacture public consent for military expansionism.

The Israeli military-industrial complex, with its reliance on Western-supplied weapons and dual-use space technology, serves as a clear example of spacewashing in action. By marketing its military and space industries as cutting-edge and innovative, Israel deflects attention from its use of these technologies to sustain occupation, eco-apartheid, and systematic violence against Palestinians. PSI highlights the importance of recognizing spacewashing as a deliberate tactic to uphold the military-industrial complex under the guise of technological progress and peaceful exploration.

3. Recommendations and Policy Considerations

The United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs (UNODA) plays a crucial role in addressing the challenges posed by military spending and its impact on sustainable development. Through research, policy advocacy, and international engagement, UNODA works to promote transparency, arms control, and disarmament as key mechanisms for reducing global militarization and reallocating resources toward peace and development. This call for papers on military expenditure and the SDGs is an important opportunity to critically examine these issues and propose actionable recommendations.

PSI's role in this discourse is to highlight how the militarization of space and defense industries intersects with systems of oppression, resource extraction, and colonial expansion, particularly in Palestine. By documenting the connections between military funding, eco-apartheid, and spacewashing, PSI aims to challenge dominant narratives that frame military-industrial activities as necessary for security and progress. Instead, we emphasize how these activities actively obstruct peace, sustainability, and self-determination for marginalized populations.

Given the above context, PSI puts forward the following five recommendations in response to UNODA's call on military expenditure:

1. **Reallocating military budgets towards sustainable development initiatives**, particularly in war-affected and occupied regions.
2. **Ending military funding structures that enable eco-apartheid and spacewashing**, ensuring that sustainability is prioritized over militarized expansionism.
3. **Strengthening international frameworks to demilitarize outer space**, ensuring that space remains a global commons dedicated to peace and sustainability.
4. **Enhancing transparency in military spending and its environmental impact**, advocating for accountability in how resources are distributed.
5. **Supporting scientific and technological self-determination in occupied territories**, ensuring access to space, technology, and research opportunities for marginalized communities.

4. Conclusion

The unchecked rise in global military expenditures undermines the achievement of the SDGs by reinforcing economic inequalities, environmental degradation, and technological disparities. Palestine stands as a stark example of how militarization obstructs sustainable development, demonstrating the urgent need for international efforts to redirect resources from militarization towards resilience-building, peace, and sustainability.

UNODA's role in addressing military expenditure is critical in fostering global accountability and policy changes that prioritize human rights and sustainable development. While UNODA and other international bodies have taken steps to highlight the risks posed by excessive military spending, further concrete actions must be implemented to ensure that military-industrial interests do not override sustainable development imperatives.

As a think tank, PSI remains committed to advocating for policy shifts that demilitarize space and reframe technological progress as a tool for peace rather than conflict. The PSI Space and Military-Industrial Complex database is one mechanism through which we seek to hold the space and defense industries accountable for their roles in sustaining militarized violence. In line with UNODA's call, PSI urges increased scrutiny and public awareness of how space technologies are weaponized and incorporated into military strategies that obstruct the SDGs.

Addressing military expenditure as a barrier to sustainable development requires a coordinated effort across research institutions, policy bodies, and civil society organizations. The international community must take urgent measures to enforce disarmament commitments, introduce regulatory frameworks that prevent the militarization of emerging technologies, and ensure that space remains a global commons for scientific and environmental cooperation rather than an extension of military dominance. Without such efforts, the vision of achieving the SDGs will remain compromised by unchecked militarization and its devastating consequences for oppressed and occupied populations worldwide.